

Role of Hydroxo Species of Lanthanides in Metal-Complex Equilibria with Xylenol Orange as a Polydentate Ligand

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Equilibrium constants in the chelation reactions between the tripositive rare earth ions: Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Eu(III), Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III), Ho(III), Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) and 3,3'-bis [N,N'-di(carboxymethyl)-aminomethyl]-*o*-cresolsulphonphthalein (xylenol orange; dcac) have been determined at 30° and at ionic strength of 0.10 [NaClO₄; NaCl in case of Ce(III)]. The effects of the existing metal hydroxo species, M(OH)²⁺, on various metal ligand equilibria have been examined. A consideration of metal hydroxo species in accounting for the changes and trends in the stabilities shows that it is essential to consider them, in cases where the association of the ligand with the metal ion is not substantial.

In a previous paper on chelation reactions of the rare earth ions with 3,3'-bis [N, N'-di(carboxymethyl)-aminomethyl]-*o*-cresolsulphonphthalein (xylenol orange; dcac)¹, the concentrations of various species present in solution and the metal-ligand equilibrium constants were calculated, without taking into account the formation of the metal hydroxo species. At low pH values where the formation of metal hydroxo species is not significant, it may reasonably be justified to ignore their existence. However, at higher pH or a pH where the association of hydroxyl ion with metal ion is appreciable the concentration of free metal ion decreases considerably, whereas the concentration of the complex species formed undergoes only a small change. Similarly, the free ligand concentration is also affected. The significant changes in the concentrations of the free metal ion and the ligand are likely to disturb the postulated metal-ligand equilibria. The concentration of the various complex species and the corresponding equilibrium constants with due regard to the formation of the metal hydroxo species need therefore be considered for a more rigorous understanding of the chelation process reported earlier. The present study is an outcome, considering all relevant factors, for the evaluation of the concentrations of the species present in solution and the determination of the stability constants, over a sufficiently large pH range, and is a part of a programme of work in these laboratories²⁻⁸ on a treatment of various types of equilibria in metal-ligand systems.

Experimental

For studying the hydrolysis, pH-metric titrations of acidified solutions of the metal ions (5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M), Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Eu(III), Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III), Ho(III), Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) against standard alkali were carried out at 30° and at ionic strength of 0.10 maintained by NaClO₄ (NaCl in case of Ce(III)). The titration curves between pH and *a* (moles of alkali used per mole of metal ion) were plotted and the stability con-

stants of the metal hydroxo species M(OH)²⁺ were determined as usual. The values are given in Table I.

For the metal ligand equilibria the values have been taken from the previous paper¹.

All the calculations for metal-ligand reactions were carried out by means of a IBM 7044 Computer.

Results and Discussion

Below pH ~5.0 (fig. 1) the existence of the following dominating equilibria is evident from the inflection of pH vs *a* curve at *a* = 3 of the metal ligand systems.

K_1 was calculated ignoring the existence of metal hydroxo species; the equilibrium (1) exists at low pH values, and the formation of the hydroxo species M(OH)²⁺ would be negligible. However a consideration of this species involves the following mass and charge balance relations.

$$C_M = [M^{3+}] + [M(OH)^{2+}] + [MH_3L] \quad (2)$$

$$C_A = [H_3L] + [H_2L^-] + [H_4L^{2-}] + [H_3L^{3-}] + [MH_3L] \quad (3)$$

$$aC_A = [H_2L^-] + 2[H_4L^{2-}] + 3[H_3L^{3-}] + 3[MH_3L] + [M(OH)^{2+}] \quad (4)$$

From equations (2) and (3):

$$[M^{3+}] = \frac{x_1 [H_3L^{3-}]}{1 + K_1 [OH^-]} = z_1 [H_3L^{3-}] \quad (5)$$

* For Correspondence.

Fig. 1. Plots of pH against moles of alkali used per mole of ligand (a):
 $C_M = C_A = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ (The curves for the other metal ion systems have not been given).

where

$$K' = \frac{[M(OH)^{3+}]}{[M^{3+}][OH^-]}$$

$$x_1 = \frac{[H^+]^3}{K_1^H K_2^H K_3^H} + \frac{[H^+]^2}{K_2^H K_3^H} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_3^H} + 1$$

$$z_1 = \frac{x_1}{1 + K'[OH^-]}$$

Substituting the value of $[MH_3L]$ from equation (3) into equation (4):

$$[H_3L^{3-}] = \frac{C_A(3-a)}{y_1 - K'z_1[OH^-]} \quad (6)$$

where,

$$y_1 = \frac{3[H^+]^3}{K_1^H K_2^H K_3^H} + \frac{2[H^+]^2}{K_2^H K_3^H} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_3^H}$$

Similarly from equation (3):

$$[MH_3L] = C_A - x_1 [H_3L^{3-}] \quad (7)$$

The values of $[M^{3+}]$, $[H_3L^{3-}]$ and $[MH_3L]$ were calculated from the equations (5), (6), and (7) respectively, and were used to calculate the equilibrium constant for reaction (1). For comparison, the equilibrium constants in both the situations (i) considering and (ii) ignoring the metal hydroxo species are given. The values obtained under both the situations are identical.

Further, between $a=3$ and 4 (above $pH \sim 5.0$), where $M(OH)^{2+}$ would be formed in considerable amount, the concentrations of various species and the equilibrium constants for the reactions :

would not remain the same as obtained without introducing the concentration terms of $M(OH)^{2+}$ species in the mass and charge balance equations. In this region

(between $a=3$ and 4), the concentrations of the species essential for the determination of equilibrium constants (K and K_2) were evaluated from the following relations.

$$C_M = [M^{3+}] + [M(OH)^{2+}] + [MH_3L] + [MH_2L^-] \quad (10)$$

$$C_A = [H_6L] + [H_5L] + [H_4L^{2-}] + [MH_3L] + [MH_2L^-] \quad (11)$$

From equations (10) and (11) :

$$[M^{3+}] = \frac{x_2[H_2L^{4-}]}{1 + K'[OH^-]} = z_2[H_2L^{4-}] \quad (12)$$

where

$$x_2 = \frac{[H^+]^4}{K_1^H K_2^H K_3^H K_4^H} + \frac{[H^+]^3}{K_2^H K_3^H K_4^H} + \frac{[H^+]^2}{K_3^H K_4^H} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_4^H} + 1 ;$$

$$z_2 = \frac{x_2}{1 + K'[OH^-]}$$

Similarly :

$$aC_A = [H_6L^-] + 2[H_4L^{2-}] + \dots + 4[H_2L^{4-}] + 3[MH_3L] + 4[MH_2L^-] + [M(OH)^{2+}] \quad (13)$$

Eliminating $[MH_2L^-]$ using equation (11) and introducing equilibrium constant K_1 and the proton dissociation constants ($K_1^H, K_2^H, K_3^H, K_4^H$) :

$$C_A(4-a) - y_2[H_2L^{4-}] + K_1 \frac{[M^{3+}][H_2L^{4-}][H^+]}{K_4^H} - K'[M^{3+}][OH^-] \quad (14)$$

Replacing $[M^{3+}]$ by $z_2[H_2L^{4-}]$:

$$C_A(4-a) = [H_2L^{4-}](y_2 - K'z_2[OH^-]) + [H_2L^{4-}]^2 \frac{K_1 z_2 [H^+]}{K_4^H} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{where } y_2 = \frac{4[H^+]^4}{K_1^H K_2^H K_3^H K_4^H} + \frac{3[H^+]^3}{K_2^H K_3^H K_4^H} + \frac{2[H^+]^2}{K_3^H K_4^H} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_4^H}$$

$[H_2L^{4-}]$ can be calculated from equation (15) which can be utilised for evaluation of $[MH_3L]$ as below :

$$[MH_3L] = \frac{K_1 z_2 [H^+][H_2L^{4-}]^2}{K_4^H} \quad (16)$$

Now from equation (11)

$$[MH_2L^-] = C_A - x_2[H_2L^{4-}] - [MH_3L] \quad (17)$$

Equations (15), (12), (16), and (17) respectively were used to evaluate $[H_2L^{4-}]$, $[M^{3+}]$, $[MH_3L]$, and $[MH_2L^-]$. Introducing these quantities into equation (9) K_2 was calculated. Similarly utilising $[H^+]$ the refined equilibrium constant value, K for the reaction

was calculated.

K_2' values obtained under these situations are slightly lower than before.

Similar expressions were obtained for other equilibria existing between different ranges of a values.

Thus :

(i) For the equilibria (between $a=4$ and 5) :

$$[M^{3+}] = \frac{x_3[HL^{5-}]}{1 + K'[OH^-]} = z_3[HL^{5-}]$$

$$C_A(5-a) = (y_3 K' z_3 [OH^-])[HL^{5-}] + \left(\frac{2K_1 z_3 [H^+]^2}{K_4^H K_5^H} + \frac{K_2 z_3 [H^+]}{K_5^H} \right) [HL^{5-}]^2 \quad (22)$$

$$[MH_3L] = \frac{K_1 z_3 [H^+]^2 [HL^{5-}]^2}{K_4^H K_5^H} \quad (23)$$

$$[MH_2L^-] = \frac{K_2 z_3 [H^+] [HL^{5-}]^2}{K_5^H} \quad (24)$$

$$[MHL^{2-}] = C_A - x_3 [HL^{5-}] - [MH_3L] - [MH_2L^-] \quad (25)$$

where

$$x_3 = \frac{[H^+]^5}{K_1^H K_2^H \dots K_5^H} + \frac{[H^+]^4}{K_2^H \dots K_5^H} + \dots + \frac{[H^+]}{K_5^H} + 1$$

$$z_3 = \frac{x_3}{1 + K'[OH^-]}$$

$$y_3 = \frac{5[H^+]^4}{K_1^H K_2^H \dots K_5^H} + \frac{4[H^+]^3}{K_2^H \dots K_5^H} + \dots + \frac{[H^+]}{K_5^H}$$

(ii) For the equilibria (between $a=5$ and 6) :

$$[M^{3+}] = \frac{y_4[L^{6-}]}{1 + K'[OH^-]} = z_4[L^{6-}] \quad (28)$$

$$C_A(6-a) = (y_4 - K' z_4 [OH^-])[L^{6-}] + \left(\frac{3K_1 z_4 [H^+]^3}{K_4^H K_5^H K_6^H} + \frac{2K_2 z_4 [H^+]^2}{K_5^H K_6^H} + \frac{K_3 z_4 [H^+]}{K_6^H} \right) [L^{6-}]^2 \quad (29)$$

$$[MH_3L] = \frac{K_1 z_4 [H^+]^3 [L^{6-}]^2}{K_4^H K_5^H K_6^H} \quad (30)$$

$$[MH_2L^-] = \frac{K_2 z_4 [H^+]^2 [L^{6-}]^2}{K_5^H K_6^H} \quad (31)$$

$$[MHL^{2-}] = \frac{K_3 z_4 [H^+] [L^{6-}]^2}{K_6^H} \quad (32)$$

$$[ML^{3-}] = C_A - x_4[L^{6-}] - [MH_3L] - [MH_2L^-] - [MHL^{2-}] \quad (33)$$

where

$$x_4 = \frac{[H^+]^6}{K_1^H K_2^H \dots K_6^H} + \frac{[H^+]^5}{K_2^H \dots K_6^H} + \dots + \frac{[H^+]}{K_6^H} + 1$$

$$z_4 = \frac{x_4}{1 + K' [OH^-]}$$

$$y_4 = \frac{6[H^+]^6}{K_1^H K_2^H \dots K_6^H} + \frac{5[H^+]^5}{K_2^H \dots K_6^H} + \dots + \frac{[H^+]}{K_6^H}$$

(iii) For the equilibria (between $a=6$ and 7):

$$C_A(7-a) = (y_6 - K' z_4 [OH^-])[L^{6-}] + \left(\frac{4K_1 z_4 [H^+]^3}{K_4^H K_5^H K_6^H} + \frac{3K_2 z_4 [H^+]^3}{K_5^H K_6^H} + \frac{2K_3 z_4 [H^+]}{K_6^H} + K' z_4 \right) [L^{6-}]^2 \quad (36)$$

$$[ML^{3-}] = K_4 z_4 [L^{6-}]^3 \quad (37)$$

$$[M(OH)L^{4-}] = C_A - x_4 [L^{6-}] - [MH_3L] - [MH_2L^-] - [MHL^{2-}] - [ML^{3-}] \quad (38)$$

where

$$y_6 = \frac{7[H^+]^6}{K_1^H K_2^H \dots K_6^H} + \frac{6[H^+]^5}{K_2^H \dots K_6^H} + \dots + \frac{2[H^+]}{K_6^H} + 1$$

Since reaction (1) is dominating below $pH \sim 5.0$, where the formation of the species $M(OH)^{2+}$ is negligible, the metal-ligand equilibrium constants obtained in both the situations (i) considering the formation of $M(OH)^{2+}$ species and (ii) ignoring the formation of metal hydroxo species are identical (table 1).

Further the reaction (9) exists between $pH \sim 5.7$ and 7.8 for La(III) and between pH 4.2 and 6.4 for Lu(III) chelates. In these ranges of pH the concentration of the species $M(OH)^{2+}$ is increased. Thus the equilibrium constants obtained for the metal chelates of La(III) to Eu(III) considering metal hydroxo species are slightly less than those obtained while ignoring the concentration of $M(OH)^{2+}$ species. The values are identical for the Y(III), Gd(III), Tb(III), and Dy(III) chelates. Again from Ho(III) to Lu(III) the previous order is followed. Similarly the proton dissociation constants for MH_3L species (reaction 8) for La(III) to Eu(III) and Ho(III) to Yb(III) chelates are slightly less when considering the metal hydroxo species, than those by ignoring the metal hydroxo species. For other metal-chelate systems the values in both the situations (i) and (ii) are identical (table 2).

Reaction (19) occurs between $a=4$ and 5 in the pH ranges 7.8–9.2 and 6.3–8.1 respectively for La(III) and Lu(III) metal-chelates. In this range a large amount of metal hydroxo species are formed. The values obtained in situation (i) deviate more from those of situation (ii). The effect is slightly pronounced for the light rare earth metal-chelates; the difference in $\log K$ values obtained under situation (i) and (ii) for La(III) chelate is 0.08, which decreases to 0.02 for Eu(III) chelate. This difference for other cases is either 0.01 or 0.02. Similar changes are observed for the dissociation of protons from MH_2L^- (reaction 20). The dissociation constants while considering the metal hydroxo species are less than those obtained from (ii).

Reaction (26) exists between $pH \sim 9.2$ and 10.7 for La(III) and ~ 8.1 and 9.5 for Lu(III) chelates. In this range of pH , a further increase in the amount of metal hydroxo species is expected due to increase in OH^- ion concentrations, but at the same time metal-ligand association will comparatively be large due to the change in the ionic charge of the ligand (i.e. HL^{5-} to L^{6-}). Here the difference of $\log K$ values in situations (i) and (ii) are comparatively smaller than those of reaction (19). The $\log K$ values in situation (ii) deviate from those in

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS FOR THE FORMATION OF VARIOUS COMPLEX SPECIES IN 1 : 1 RARE EARTH - DCAC MIXTURE (30°; $\mu=0.1M$)

Metal Ion	log K for reactions						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Y(III)	6.84	5.30	7.70	10.24	11.96	15.37	(i)
...	...	5.30	7.70	10.25	11.96	15.37	(ii)
La(III)	5.70	4.35	5.81	7.53	8.64	11.28	(i)
...	...	4.35	5.82	7.61	8.71	11.36	(ii)
Ce(III)	5.82	4.35	6.01	7.83	9.00	11.75	(i)
...	...	4.35	6.02	7.88	9.03	11.79	(ii)
Pr(III)	5.98	4.59	6.27	8.16	9.37	12.22	(i)
...	...	4.59	6.28	8.20	9.40	12.26	(ii)
Nd(III)	6.08	4.74	6.50	8.47	9.79	12.80	(i)
...	...	4.74	6.51	8.51	9.82	12.82	(ii)
Sm(III)	6.24	4.89	6.88	8.90	10.38	13.46	(i)
...	...	4.89	6.88	8.92	10.39	13.47	(ii)
Eu(III)	6.35	4.91	6.92	9.03	10.50	13.65	(i)
...	...	4.91	6.93	9.05	10.51	13.65	(ii)
Gd(III)	6.48	5.06	7.20	9.45	11.05	14.26	(i)
...	...	5.06	7.20	9.46	11.05	14.26	(ii)
Tb(III)	6.66	5.12	7.35	9.72	11.33	14.67	(i)
...	...	5.12	7.35	9.73	11.33	14.66	(ii)
Dy(III)	6.76	5.22	7.54	9.98	11.63	15.00	(i)
...	...	5.22	7.54	9.99	11.63	14.99	(ii)
Ho(III)	7.04	5.38	7.88	10.58	12.39	15.96	(i)
...	...	5.38	7.89	10.59	12.39	15.96	(ii)
Er(III)	7.28	5.45	8.11	10.94	12.93	16.60	(i)
...	...	5.45	8.11	10.95	12.93	16.60	(ii)
Tm(III)	7.48	5.54	8.32	11.21	13.27	17.04	(i)
...	...	5.54	8.33	11.23	13.28	17.05	(ii)
Yb(III)	7.60	5.64	8.54	11.56	13.74	17.60	(i)
...	...	5.64	8.55	11.58	13.76	17.62	(ii)
Lu(III)	7.80	5.74	8.80	11.86	14.11	18.35	(i)
...	...	5.74	8.81	11.87	14.11	18.33	(ii)

Reactions : (1) $M^{3+} + OH^- \rightleftharpoons M(OH)^{2+}$; (2) $M^{3+} + H_2L^{3-} \rightleftharpoons MH_2L$; (3) $M^{3+} + H_2L^{4-} \rightleftharpoons MH_2L^-$;
 (4) $M^{3+} + HL^{3-} \rightleftharpoons MHL^{2-}$; (5) $M^{3+} + L^{4-} \rightleftharpoons ML^{3-}$; (6) $M^{3+} + L^{4-} + OH^- \rightleftharpoons M(OH)L^{4-}$

- (i) Values obtained while taking the metal hydroxo species into account.
 (ii) Values obtained ignoring metal hydroxo species.

situation (i) from La(III) to Eu(III) chelates. The deviation for La(III) chelate is maximum, and decreases as the atomic number increases. Except Tm(III) and Yb(III) chelates, where the above difference of log *K* values is respectively 0.01 and 0.02, equilibrium constants obtained in situations (i) and (ii) are identical. For reaction (27) the difference in log *K* values of situation (i) and (ii) vary from 0 to 0.02. Such changes in equilibrium constants for reaction (34) are also almost similar to reaction (26).

These results show that for lesser association between metal and ligand, the change in equilibrium constant is large, while it is small for larger metal ligand association even at higher pH, where the free metal ion concentration (the essential parameter for the evaluation of the equilibrium constant) is largely altered due to the formation of M(OH)²⁺ species.

The proton dissociation constants for the rare earth-dcac chelates were also calculated considering 100% metal ligand association (table 2). The values obtained are comparatively lower than those under situations (i) and (ii).

(Table 2—Contd.)

Gd(III)	6.06	8.10	9.40	3.21 (i)
	6.06	8.09	9.41	3.21 (ii)
	6.15	8.15	9.52	3.16 (iii)
Tb(III)	5.97	7.98	9.38	3.36 (i)
	5.97	7.97	9.39	3.35 (ii)
	6.04	8.02	9.50	3.21 (iii)
Dy(III)	5.89	7.89	9.35	3.37 (i)
	5.89	7.89	9.36	3.36 (ii)
	5.96	7.93	9.42	3.27 (iii)
Ho(III)	5.70	7.65	9.11	3.59 (i)
	5.69	7.65	9.11	3.59 (ii)
	5.78	7.70	9.23	3.46 (iii)
Er(III)	5.55	7.52	9.02	3.67 (i)
	5.54	7.51	9.03	3.67 (ii)
	5.61	7.57	9.09	3.63 (iii)
Tm(III)	5.42	7.46	8.96	3.80 (i)
	5.41	7.46	8.97	3.80 (ii)
	5.47	7.50	9.04	3.73 (iii)
Yb(III)	5.30	7.33	8.82	3.86 (i)
	5.29	7.33	8.83	3.86 (ii)
	5.36	7.37	8.88	3.81 (iii)
Lu(III)	5.17	7.28	8.75	3.93 (i)
	5.17	7.28	8.76	3.93 (ii)
	5.24	7.32	8.80	3.89 (iii)

TABLE 2. PROTON DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS FOR RARE EARTH-DCAC CHELATES (30°; μ = 0.1M).

Metal Ion	Log <i>K</i> for Reactions			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Y(III)	5.81	7.81	9.32	3.42 (i)
	5.80	7.81	9.33	3.41 (ii)
	5.89	7.82	9.36	3.35 (iii)
La(III)	6.74	8.53	9.86	2.64 (i)
	6.73	8.48	9.87	2.65 (ii)
	6.92	8.67	10.03	2.52 (iii)
Ce(III)	6.54	8.57	9.83	2.75 (i)
	6.53	8.53	9.85	2.76 (ii)
	6.71	8.62	9.93	2.61 (iii)
Pr(III)	6.55	8.46	9.79	2.85 (i)
	6.54	8.43	9.80	2.86 (ii)
	6.62	8.48	9.90	2.74 (iii)
Nd(III)	6.42	8.37	9.68	3.01 (i)
	6.41	8.35	9.69	3.00 (ii)
	6.50	8.42	9.77	2.86 (iii)
Sm(III)	7.22	8.34	9.53	3.08 (i)
	7.21	8.32	9.54	3.08 (ii)
	7.35	8.34	9.62	3.04 (iii)
Eu(III)	6.19	8.26	9.51	3.15 (i)
	6.18	8.25	9.52	3.14 (ii)
	6.31	8.30	9.60	3.08 (iii)

Reactions: (1) $MH_2L \rightleftharpoons MH_2L^- + H^+$; (2) $MH_2L \rightleftharpoons MHL^{2+} + H^+$; (3) $MHL^{2+} \rightleftharpoons ML^{3+} + H^+$; (4) $ML^{3+} + OH^- \rightleftharpoons M(OH)L^{2+}$

(i) Values obtained while taking the metal hydroxo species into account.

(ii) Values obtained ignoring metal hydroxo species.

(iii) Values obtained assuming 100% metal ligand association.

In fig. 2 the percentage distribution of a few typical ions Y(III), La(III), and Lu(III) have been plotted against pH. It indicates the presence of insignificant amounts of Y(III), La(III) and Lu(III) ions respectively above a pH 8.0, 9.4, and 6.6. Considerable amounts of Y(OH)²⁺ and Lu(OH)²⁺ exist between the pH ranges ~5.5–11.0, and ~4.4–9.0 respectively. Formation of La(OH)²⁺ occurs at pH ~6.6 in significant amounts. The concentration increases upto pH ~9.6 and then decreases. The curves for the total metal ions attached with dcac have also been plotted against pH (fig. 2). It shows that at pH ~9.0 and 11.0 respectively for Lu(III) and Y(III) chelates nearly the whole of the metal ion is attached with dcac, while in the case of La(III)-dcac system only 94% of the metal ion is associated with the ligand at pH 11.0.

(Contd.)

